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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF PULSATILE DRUG
DELIVERY SYSTEM OF SIMVASTATIN****Dr. Nallamolu Bala Venkata Siva Ram ***, Mandapati Jaswanth Kumar, Potla Rahul,
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Nagar, Eluru, Duggirala, Andhra Pradesh - 534007**Abstract:**

In the present research work, we have designed a pulsatile formulation of Simvastatin to treat dyslipidemia pattern of the disease. Core tablets were prepared by incorporating different concentration of disintegrants and were compressed in between different concentration of polymers. The core and compression coated tablets were subjected to pre-formulation, physicochemical and In-vitro drug release studies. Core formulations, characterized by different release rates and mechanisms, will be coated by compression with an outer shell of different polymeric barrier layers of polymers. The coatings prevent drug release from the core until the polymeric shell is completely eroded or swollen. FTIR studies revealed that there was not any chemical reaction between pure drug Simvastatin and polymers. The pre and post-compressional parameters of tablets were also found to be within limits. Our optimized formulation F-3 releases Simvastatin 100.15 % up to 12 hours.

Key words: Pulsatile formulation, Simvastatin, Sodium starch glycolate, Chitosan, Eudragit RSPO, HPMC K 100 and Compression coated tablets.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral controlled drug delivery systems represent the most popular form of controlled drug delivery systems for the obvious advantages of oral route of drug administration. Such systems release the drug with constant or variable release rates. These dosage forms offer many advantages, such as nearly constant drug level at the site of action, prevention of peak-valley fluctuations, reduction in dose of drug, reduced dosage frequency, avoidance of side effects, and improved patient compliance.^{1,2,3} The principle rationale for the use of pulsatile release is for the drugs where a constant drug release, i.e., a zero-order release is not desired. The release of the drug as a pulse after a lag time (an interval of no drug release) has to be designed in such a way that a complete and rapid drug release follows the lag time. Pulsatile release is also useful for the targeting of the drug irritating the stomach or degradable therein, as well for drugs developing biological tolerance or with an extensive first-pass metabolism. Conventional controlled release drug delivery systems are based on single or multiple-unit reservoir or matrix systems, which are designed to provide constant or nearly constant drug levels over an extended period of time.^{4,5} The temporal rhythms of body functions have been shown to affect not only the severity of a number of diseases but also the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of most bioactive compounds in use. Accordingly, chronotherapeutic treatments, tailored to supply the patient with the appropriate dose of the required drug at the perfect time, are gaining an increasing interest. Many diseases follow a well-defined circadian pattern such as hypertension, allergic rhinitis, osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, nocturnal asthma, angina pectoris and peptic ulcer.^{6,7}

Pulsatile drug delivery system (PDDS) can be defined as a system where drug is released suddenly after a well-defined lag time according to the circadian rhythm of the disease. PDDS can be classified according to the pulseregulation of drug release into three main classes; time-controlled pulsatile release (single or multiple unit system), internal stimuli-induced release and external stimuli-induced pulsatile release systems. PDDS can also be classified according to the dosage form into three main types; capsules, pellets and tablets among which the 'core-in-cup' tablet system. The core-in-cup tablet system consists of three different parts: a core tablet, containing the active ingredient, an impermeable outer shell and a top cover plug layer of a soluble polymer.⁸

In the field of oral delivery, besides a widespread use of pro-longed-release dosage forms increasing interest has been focused on the development of formulations able to release active pharmaceutical ingredients after programmed lag times or to specific regions of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. The time-dependent approach, in particular, is based on the relatively constant small intestinal transit time (SITT; 3 ± 1 h standard error) of dosage forms.⁹

On the contrary, the duration of gastric residence of solid dosage forms, which depends on their size and density as well as fasted or fed conditions of subjects, is unpredictable; hence, by the application of an outer gastro-resistant layer, which dissolves only after the dosage form is emptied from the stomach, the influence of variable gastric emptying can be overcome. Subsequently, a lag phase imparted to the drug-containing core allows the system to reach delay duration comparable to SITT.

Figure 1.1: Pulsatile core-in-cup tablet

Among time-based devices, a platform for delayed and site-specific release of drugs in the form of a reservoir system, named Chronotopic™, has already been developed. Such device is based on single- or multiple-unit drug cores (tablets, capsules, pellets) coated with a functional layer composed of swellable/erodible polymers (namely, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, HPMC) of few hundred microns of thickness applied by different techniques (press-coating, spraycoating and powder layering). When intended for time-based drug delivery, an outer enteric film is subsequently applied. Once the device is emptied from the stomach, the enteric coating dissolves and the HPMC-based layer delays the contact of the biological fluids with the core, allowing the release of the drug only after a programmed period of time. The effectiveness of the Chronotopic™ system, its flexibility in terms of duration of the lag phase, both in vitro and in vivo, as well as the possibility of scaling up the manufacturing process has been demonstrated. A step forward in the development of the Chronotopic™ system was represented by a

capsular device (Chronocap™) that combined the release functionality of the polymeric coating with the ability to convey a variety of drug preparations (solid, semi-solid, liquid), thus bringing about both technical and regulatory advantages.¹⁰⁻¹²

Pulsatile delivery is generally intended as a release of the active ingredient that is delayed for a programmable period of time to meet particular chronotherapeutic needs and, in the case of oral administration, also target distal intestinal regions, such as the colon. Most oral pulsatile delivery platforms consist in coated formulations wherein the applied polymer serves as the release-controlling agent. When exposed to aqueous media, the coating initially performs as a protective barrier and, subsequently, undergoes a timely failure based on diverse mechanisms depending on its physico-chemical and formulation characteristics. Indeed, it may be ruptured because of the gradual expansion of the core, swell and/or erode due to the glassy-rubbery polymer transition or become permeable thus allowing the drug molecules to diffuse outwards. Otherwise, when the coating is a semi permeable membrane provided with one or more orifices, the drug is released through the latter as a result of an osmotic water influx. The vast majority of pulsatile delivery systems described so far have been prepared by spray-coating, which offers important versatility and feasibility advantages over other techniques such as pressand dip-coating.^{13,14}

Pulsatile delivery systems are non-conventional dosage forms designed to release the active ingredient after a lag phase of programmable duration thereby allowing a chronotherapeutic effect to be attained. Most current pulsatile delivery systems are typically time-controlled in that the onset of release is prompted by inherent mechanisms irrespective of the differing conditions they may encounter in the outer environment. Among them, formulations intended for the oral route are of particular interest in the case of chronic pathologies with circadian symptoms that have a high likelihood of recurring in the night or early morning hours, such as cardiovascular disease, bronchial asthma, rheumatoid arthritis and sleep disorders. Indeed, medications able to provide an appropriate delay phase prior to drug release, administered at bedtime, could selectively cover the especially critical period during which the disease

state tends to worsen with no need for waking up the patient for drug intake. In addition, oral pulsatile delivery devices, particularly when able to yield multi-pulse release profiles, may serve in place of prolonged-release systems with drugs that are subject to a strong first-pass metabolism or develop pharmacological tolerance and, in the specific case of antibiotics, would limit the growth of resistant bacterial strains by circumventing defensive dormancy and affecting a larger number of micro-organisms in the division phase. Moreover, it has recently been suggested that the use of pulsatile release dosage forms could prevent detrimental interactions between co-administered drugs from occurring within the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. Although the earliest pulsatile delivery formulations were devised as multi-layer tablets partially enclosed in an impermeable shell, a timed liberation of orally-administered bioactive compounds is currently achieved mainly by the application of a functional polymeric coating to a drug-containing core. The core may either be a single- or a multiple-unit dosage form, the latter enabling improved reproducibility in the GI transit and absorption consistency. The performance of the coating strictly depends on the relevant physico-chemical nature and is started on exposure to the aqueous biological fluids (solvent activation).¹⁵

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Simvastatin Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar
Sodium starch glycolate Yarrow Chem. Products, Mumbai,
Chitosan S.D. Fine chemicals limited (Hyderabad)
Eudragit RSPO SD Fine Chemicals, Mumbai
HPMC K 100 S.D. Fine chemicals limited (Hyderabad)
PVP K30 FMC Biopolymers.
Magnesium Stearate Himedia Chem Lab, Mumbai.

METHODOLOGY:

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The compatibility between the pure drug and excipients was detected by FTIR spectra obtained on Bruker FTIR Germany (Alpha T). The solid powder sample directly place on yellow crystal which was made up of ZnSe. The spectra were recorded over the wave number of 4000 cm⁻¹ to 550 cm⁻¹.

Formulation development of Tablets:**Table 7.1: Formulation development of core tablets**

Ingredients	C1	C2	C3
Simvastatin	10	10	10
Sodium starch glycolate	20	40	60
PVP K 30	8	8	8
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5
Talc	4	4	4
Microcrystalline cellulose	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
Total weight	120	120	120

Table 7.2: Formulations for press coated tablets

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Chitosan	15	30	45	-	-	-	-	-	-
Eudragit RSPO	-	-	-	15	30	45	-	-	-
HPMC K 100	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	30	45
PVP K30	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Magnesium Stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Microcrystalline cellulose	Q.S								
Talc	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Total weight	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

6.4 Evaluation Parameters**6.4.1 Pre compression parameters**

The quality of tablet, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.

Angle of repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as, the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile

until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully pored through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

$$\tan \theta = \text{Angle of repose}$$

h = Height of the cone, r = Radius of the cone base

Table 7.3: Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk density
Tapped density
Measures of powder compressibility

Table 7.4: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Passable
2 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Post compression parameters of core and press coated tablets

The tablets after punching of every batch were evaluated for in-process and finished product quality control tests i.e. thickness, weight uniformity test, hardness, friability, drug content and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Hardness

Thickness

Friability test

Weight variation test

8.1. Preformulation Studies

Table 8.1: Calibration data of Simvastatin 0.1N HCL

Concentration [$\mu\text{g/ml}$]	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.158
10	0.291
15	0.432
20	0.554
25	0.681

Fig:8.1: Standard Graph of Simvastatin in 0.1N HCL

In vitro drug release of Simvastatin core tablets

In vitro dissolution studies were carried out using USP XXIII Type II (paddle method) apparatus. pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was used as dissolution medium. Release pattern was studied visually by taking sample of 5 mL at the specific time intervals. Also the sample was analyzed at 238 nm for 6.8 phosphate buffer using a UV spectrophotometer.

Table.8.6: Mechanism of drug release as per Kormeyer equation / peppa's model

S.No	n value	Drug Release
1.	$n < 0.5$	Fickian release
2.	$0.5 < n < 1$	Non-Fickian release
3.	$n > 1$	Case II transport

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Present study was done on pulsatile tablets with different formulations F1 to F9. Formulations had weight ratio of polymers like Chitosan, Eudragit RSPO, HPMC K 100 along with various excipients. This section gives detailed description of the results and discussion on pulsatile Simvastatin tablets.

Table 8.2: Calibration data of Simvastatin in pH6.8 phosphate buffer

Conc [µg/ml]	Abs
0	0
5	0.132
10	0.259
15	0.362
20	0.476
25	0.585

Fig. 8.2: Standard Graph of Simvastatin in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer

7.3: FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometry)

Fig: 8.3. FTIR spectra of Simvastatin pure drug

Fig: 8. 4. FTIR spectra of Optimized Formula

Table 8.3: Pre compression parameters of Cap core tablets

Formulation Code	Bulk Density(gm/cm ²)	Tap Density (gm/cm ²)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner ratio	Angle Of Repose(Θ)
C1	0.307±0.07	0.310±0.05	14.7±0.06	1.17±0.05	23.7±0.11
C2	0.304±0.09	0.341±0.09	11.4±0.05	1.14±0.07	23.4±0.08
C3	0.301±0.09	0.371±0.11	15.1±0.09	1.11±0.05	24.1±0.16

Table 8.4: Post compression parameters of Core tablet:

Formulation code	Average Weight (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	<i>In vitro</i> disintegration time (sec)
C1	119.95	4.2	0.50	3.12	98.30	51
C2	120.26	4.9	0.36	3.24	99.62	43
C3	119.14	4.1	0.41	3.02	99.81	19

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

Table 8.5: Pre compression Parameters of Simvastatin coated Tablets

Formulation code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	25.56±0.3	0.57±0.01	0.61±0.01	10.11±0.8	1.13±0.02
F2	24.67±0.3	0.53±0.01	0.68±0.03	10.23±0.5	1.12±0.03
F3	25.56±0.2	0.52±0.06	0.64±0.03	10.34±1.0	1.14±0.06
F4	23.30±0.1	0.50±0.21	0.66±0.12	10.23±0.5	1.12±0.06
F5	22.56±0.1	0.65±0.02	0.59±0.02	11.23±0.8	1.11±0.05
F6	23.89±0.2	0.50±0.04	0.68±0.04	11.34±0.6	1.14±0.03
F7	26.54±0.1	0.59±0.04	0.64±0.05	10.12±0.7	1.13±0.09
F8	23.67±0.3	0.58±0.12	0.58±0.04	10.23±1.0	1.11±0.07
F9	24.34±0.4	0.56±0.02	0.54±0.01	10.23±0.8	1.13±0.02

7.5. Post compression parameters for tablets

Table 8.6: Post compression parameters of Coated tablet:

Formulation code	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%loss)	Drug content (%)
F1	99.39	4.6	5.15	0.34	99.27
F2	98.72	4.8	5.69	0.46	98.64
F3	100.01	5.1	5.81	0.29	100.05
F4	98.25	4.0	5.79	0.62	99.82
F5	97.66	5.2	5.56	0.72	97.19
F6	96.85	4.9	5.11	0.69	98.52
F7	98.50	5.6	5.29	0.28	99.13
F8	98.21	4.5	5.50	0.47	97.68
F9	99.15	4.8	5.74	0.52	98.49

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

In Vitro Drug release studies of Simvastatin core tablet:

Table 8.7. Drug release of Simvastatin core tablets

Time (min)	C1	C2	C3
0	0	0	0
5	20.90	35.20	48.25
10	45.41	48.61	60.71
15	50.36	62.30	75.89
20	60.16	73.42	81.92
30	69.11	83.19	89.14
45	76.02	90.47	96.06
60	88.14	95.36	98.54

Fig: 8.5 Cumulative % drug released of Simvastatin core tablets

Table 8.8: Cumulative % drug release of Coated Simvastatin tablets containing Chitosan

Time (hr)	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
0.5	32.62	28.38	16.23
1	45.81	33.14	24.38
2	52.20	46.63	35.79
3	56.39	52.82	40.88
4	63.85	60.40	47.54
5	70.34	68.09	58.17
6	87.13	75.46	64.62
7	90.91	81.02	73.93
8	98.28	88.59	78.87
9		92.36	82.26
10		98.11	87.15
11			91.02
12			100.15

Fig: 8.6: Cumulative % drug release study of Simvastatin pulsatile tablets (F1, F2 & F3)
 Table 8.9: Cumulative % drug release of Coated Simvastatin tablets containing Eudragit RSPO

Time (hr)	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0
0.5	44.97	21.82	20.31
1	60.65	36.31	32.38
2	78.16	41.23	36.43
3	80.98	56.96	41.86
4	86.29	64.35	59.75
5	92.73	72.02	65.46
6	97.22	80.75	71.13
7		88.13	78.16
8		96.84	85.77
9			90.85
10			93.49
11			98.88
12			

Fig 8.7: Cumulative % drug release study of Simvastatin pulsatile tablets (F4, F5 & F6)

Table 8.10: Cumulative % drug release of Coated Simvastatin tablets containing HPMC K 100

Time (hr)	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0
0.5	11.22	13.49	9.07
1	17.38	15.21	13.31
2	22.45	19.07	21.03
3	29.59	26.17	24.12
4	37.83	35.56	31.13
5	43.26	42.58	39.09
6	53.15	51.27	48.17
7	61.29	59.68	55.24
8	66.76	67.37	64.36
9	73.27	71.77	68.81
10	78.19	77.42	75.63
11	84.64	82.12	79.43
12	95.49	89.28	87.19

Fig 8.8 : Cumulative % drug release study of Simvastatin pulsatile tablets (F7, F8, F9)

RELEASE KINETICS:

Table 8.11: Release kinetics and correlation coefficients (R²)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
16.23	0.5	0.707	1.210	0.301	1.923	32.460	0.0616	-0.790	83.77	4.642	4.376	0.266
24.38	1	1.000	1.387	0.000	1.879	24.380	0.0410	-0.613	75.62	4.642	4.229	0.413
35.79	2	1.414	1.554	0.301	1.808	17.895	0.0279	-0.446	64.21	4.642	4.004	0.637
40.88	3	1.732	1.612	0.477	1.772	13.627	0.0245	-0.388	59.12	4.642	3.896	0.746
47.54	4	2.000	1.677	0.602	1.720	11.885	0.0210	-0.323	52.46	4.642	3.743	0.898
58.17	5	2.236	1.765	0.699	1.621	11.634	0.0172	-0.235	41.83	4.642	3.471	1.170
64.62	6	2.449	1.810	0.778	1.549	10.770	0.0155	-0.190	35.38	4.642	3.283	1.359
73.93	7	2.646	1.869	0.845	1.416	10.561	0.0135	-0.131	26.07	4.642	2.965	1.676
78.87	8	2.828	1.897	0.903	1.325	9.859	0.0127	-0.103	21.13	4.642	2.765	1.877
82.26	9	3.000	1.915	0.954	1.249	9.140	0.0122	-0.085	17.74	4.642	2.608	2.034
87.15	10	3.162	1.940	1.000	1.109	8.715	0.0115	-0.060	12.85	4.642	2.342	2.299
91.02	11	3.317	1.959	1.041	0.953	8.275	0.0110	-0.041	8.98	4.642	2.079	2.563
100.15	12	3.464	2.001	1.079		8.346	0.0100	0.001	-0.15	4.642	0.531	5.173

Fig 8.9: Zero order plot of optimized formulation

Fig 8.10: First order plot of optimized formulation

Fig 8.11: Higuchi plot of optimized formulation

Fig 8.12: Koresmeyer-peppas plot of optimized formulation

This formulation was following Koresmeyer-peppas release mechanism with regression value of 0.994.

CONCLUSION:

- ✓ A chronomodulated drug delivery system for Simvastatin for the treatment of dyslipidemia was successfully developed. The system was found to be satisfactory in terms of release of the drug after a lag time of 2 hrs.
- ✓ The formulation (F3) Chitosan (45mg) gave satisfactory release lag time of 2 hrs and it was found to be successful in achieving pulsatile drug delivery.
- ✓ The technology (press-coating) used for the preparation of press-coated pulsatile tablets is a relatively simple manufacturing process which can be easily adopted in industrial units on a commercial scale.
- ✓ From formulation C1-C3 Simvastatin core tablets, C3 showed faster drug release than the other formulations. Faster drug release can be correlated with the high disintegration time. So, C3 formulation was selected as best formulation for further press coating and enteric coating formulations. Among All Formulations F3 was showed maximum % drug release 100.15 % at 12 hours. Hence F3 Formulation was considered as optimized Formulation.

REFERENCES:

1. Trupti Shashikant Jadhav, Nilima A. Thombre, Sanjay J. Kshirsagar. Pulsatile drug delivery system using core-in-cup approach: a review. June 2016; vol. 3 (Issue 3): 288-304.
2. Chien YW. Novel drug delivery system. 2nd ed, Marcel Decker Inc., New York; 2005: 1-3.
3. Davis SS, Illum L. Drug delivery systems for challenging molecules. *Int J Pharm.* 1998;176:1-8.
4. Bussemer T, Bodmeier RA. Drug delivery Pulsatile. *Encyclopaedia of pharmaceutical technology*; 2006: 1287-1297.
5. Bjorn L. The importance of circadian rhythms on drug response in hypertension and coronary heart diseases. *Pharmacology and therapeutics.* 2006;111:629-65.
6. Roy P, Shahiwala A. Multiparticulate formulation approach to pulsatile drug delivery current perspective. *J Controlled Rel.* 2009;134:74-80.
7. Smolensky MH, Lemmer B et al. Chronobiology and chronotherapeutics of allergic rhinitis and bronchial asthma. *Ame J Res Cri Care Med.* 2007;59:852-82.
8. Fort J. Celecoxib, a COX-2-specific inhibitor: the clinical data. *Am J Orthop.* 1999;28(3):13-8.
9. Prashant AB, Bushetti SS, Najmuddin M. Formulation and evaluation of pulsatile drug delivery system of Metoprolol tartarate using core in cup tablet. *Am J Med Med Sci.* 2012;2(6):114-22.
10. Gao W, Zhonghong WU, Chen Q, Bin YU. Preparation of Candesartan cexelxtil core in cup tablets with pulsatile release properties and its effects on the blood pressure of rabbits. *J China Pharm Uni.* 2010;41(2):124-9.
11. Khadabadi SS, Nahid HC, Farhan MK, Akeel AT. Formulation and evaluation of press coated tablet of ketoprofen- a chronotherapeutic approach. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2012;5(3):733-40.
12. Li CJ, Zhu JB, Yu WY. Preparation of verapamil hydrochloride core-in-cup tablets with double-pulsatile and multi-phasic release. 2008;43(6):652-6.
13. Archana SP, Panchaxari MD, Vinayak SM, Anand PG, Basavaraj KN. Development and characterization of chronomodulated drug delivery system of captopril. *Int J Pharm Inv.* 2011;1(4):227-33.
14. Rane AB, Gattani SG, Kadam VD, Tekade AR. Formulation and evaluation of press coated tablets for pulsatile drug delivery using hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers. *Chem Pharm Bull (Tokyo).* 2009;57(11):1213-7.
15. Swati J, Monali S, Ajay B, Janardan L, Bhanudas K, Anuruddha C. Development of pulsatile release tablets of atenolol with swelling and rupturable layers. *Int J Pharm.* 2010;2(3):31-40.
16. Rane AB, Gattani SG, Kadam VD, Tekade AR. Formulation and evaluation of press coated tablets for pulsatile drug delivery using hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers. *Chem Pharm Bull (Tokyo).* 2009;57(11):1213-7.
17. Mastiholimath VS, Dandagi PM, Samata SJ, Gadad AP, Kulkarni AR. Time and pH dependent colon specific, pulsatile delivery of theophylline for nocturnal asthma, *Int journal pharma.* 2007;328: 49-56.
18. Narisawa S, Nagata M, Danyoshi C, Yoshino H, Murata K, Hirakawa Y, et al. An organic acid induced sigmoidal release system for oral controlled-release preparations. *Pharma Research.* 1994;11(1):111-6.
19. Ramesh d,parmar, rajesh k,parikh,g.vidyasagar,dhaval. Pulsatile drug delivery systems. *International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and nanotechnology* 2009;3:605-611.
20. Yui n, okano t and sakurai y. In flammation responsive degradation of cross linked hyaluronic acid gels. *Journal of controlled release* 1992;22:105-116.
21. Donthireddy Sushma. Formulation and Evaluation of Press Coated Tablets for Pulsatile Drug Delivery. *J Biomed Syst Emerg Technol,*

Volume 8:5, 2021.

22. A Vijaya Madhavi, D Rama Brahma Reddy, M Venugopal, N Srihari, P Chenniah, P Koteswarao. Formulation and Evaluation of Pulsatile Drug Delivery System of Zafirlukast. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*. 2020; 10(2):122-128.
23. B. Manjula, V. Divyasri, Ch. Shravya, Ch. Maniteja Yadav, Ch. Soujanya. Formulation and Evaluation of Pulsatile Drug Delivery System of Lisinopril. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*. 2019; 9(2):76-82.
24. Manish Kumar Gupta, Swarnlata Saraf. Formulation and Evaluation of Pulsatile Drug Delivery System of Ramipril for Controlling Morning Spate of B.P. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Volume 17, Issue 1, Jan-Mar, 2018.
25. Chiranjibi Adhikari, Gururaj S Kulkarni, Shivakumar Swamy. Formulation And Evaluation Of Pulsatile Drug Delivery System Of Salbutamol Sulfate For The Chronotherapy Of Asthma. Vol 11, Issue 9, 2018